

PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO DIFFERENTIATED ABILITY LEARNERS IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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***Annotation:** in the given article the problem of teaching English at mixed classes and its solution is studied. One of the greatest challenges experienced by teachers teaching students who learn English as a foreign or a second language is teaching a class consisting of fast learners and slow learners commonly referred to as mixed-ability classes. In our days every student requires an individual approach according to the abilities shown. One should get an extra task so as not to be bored, another barely manages to follow the lesson, yet another needs a lesser task and some extra attention. It recommends that teachers should have healthy and supportive relationships with students and maintain a balance between emotional and intellectual interactions with them. It states that teachers should teach, shape, encourage and recreate a mind that is capable of coping with challenges and overcoming problems in today's environment.*

***Keywords:** mixed-ability class, instructional methods, discussions, problem-solving tasks, personality, student's nomination, extra task, fast learners, slow learners weaker students, extra attention.*

***Аннотация:** в данной статье изучается проблема преподавания английского языка в смешанных классах и ее решение. Одной из самых больших проблем, с которыми сталкиваются учителя, обучающие студентов, изучающих английский как иностранный или второй язык, является обучение в классе, состоящем из быстро обучающихся и медленно обучающихся,*

обычно называемых классами со смешанными способностями. В наши дни к каждому ученику необходим индивидуальный подход в соответствии с проявленными способностями. Кому-то нужно дать дополнительное задание, чтобы не скучать, другому едва удастся уследить за уроком, третьему нужно задание поменьше и дополнительное внимание. что учителя должны иметь здоровые и поддерживающие отношения с учениками и поддерживать баланс между эмоциональным и интеллектуальным взаимодействием с ними. В нем говорится, что учителя должны учить, формировать, поощрять и воссоздавать ум, способный справляться с трудностями и преодолевать проблемы в сегодняшней среде.

Ключевые слова: *разно способный класс, методы обучения, дискуссии, проблемные задачи, личность, номинация учащегося, дополнительное задание, быстро учащиеся, медленно учащиеся, более слабые учащиеся, дополнительное внимание.*

Annotatsiya: *ushbu maqolada aralash sinflarda ingliz tilini o'qitish muammosi va uning yechimi o'rganilgan. Ingliz tilini chet tili yoki ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganayotgan talabalarga o'rgatuvchi o'qituvchilar duch keladigan eng katta qiyinchiliklardan biri bu tez o'rganuvchilar va sekin o'rganuvchilardan iborat sinfni odatda aralash qobiliyatli sinflarda dars o'tkazishdir.*

Hozirgi vaqtlarda har bir talaba ko'rsatilgan qobiliyatiga qarab individual yondashuvni talab qiladi. Birovi zerikmaslik uchun qo'shimcha topshiriq olishi kerak, boshqasi esa darsni zo'rg'a kuzatib boradi, boshqasiga esa kamroq vazifa va qo'shimcha e'tibor kerak. Bunda o'qituvchilarga talabalar bilan sog'lom va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi munosabatlarga ega bo'lishlari va ular bilan hissiy va intellektual o'zaro munosabatlar o'rtasidagi muvozanatni saqlashlari tavsiya etiladi. Unda ta'kidlanishicha, o'qituvchilar bugungi sharoitda qiyinchiliklarga dosh berishga va muammolarni yengishga qodir bo'lgan ongni o'rgatishlari, shakllantirishlari, rag'batlantirishlari va qayta yaratishlari kerakligi bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: aralash qobiliyatli sinf, o'qitish usullari, muhokamalar, muammoli vazifalar, shaxsiyat, talaba nominatsiyasi, qo'shimcha topshiriq, tez o'rganuvchilar, sekin o'rganuvchilar zaif o'quvchilar, qo'shimcha e'tibor.

Introduction. An understanding of and a command over English language is the most important determinant of access to higher education, employment possibilities and social opportunities. Education has been the primary element in the more formal transmission of English around the world. English is a symbol of learners' aspirations for quality in education and it plays the major role in the field of communication globally. Language learning is a natural procedure for the natives. One of the greatest challenges experienced by teachers teaching students who learn English as a foreign or a second language is teaching a class consisting of fast learners and slow learners commonly referred to as mixed-ability classes. But for the students of other languages, deliberate efforts are required to learn a foreign language. The students of rural and semi-urban areas in Uzbekistan face such problems because English is not their mother-tongue. Presently, the most of the institutions are with mixed ability students of different levels of attention, interest, learning styles, speed, maturity, types of intelligence which pose challenges to teachers. Now in the rural and semi-urban areas, study of English language begins at an early age.

Main part. In Mixed ability level teaching, the teacher has to follow different strategies of teaching to every learner, who have different potentialities, skills, interests and learning needs. It is well known that every student has a different way of learning, and learns and progresses at different speeds. Though most institutions are usually multi-ability level, teachers find teaching such classes a very difficult and demanding task as it involves planning lessons which include a rich diversity of tasks corresponding to a variety of learning styles and abilities. It is very difficult to

teach a class with clearly different levels of language competency. They may have different starting levels of English or they may learn at very different speeds.

Nowadays, the English language teachers throughout the world keep on buzzing a word that their students are in mixed level. In the past teachers may well have said that the problem was just that some students were cleverer or simply 'better' than others in the class. But we now understand that the situation is more complex than that. Our students are indeed mixed in many ways. They are different in terms of their levels of: Attention, Interest, Motivation, Learning styles, Types of intelligences, Physiological needs, Speed, Maturity, World knowledge. The classroom is the only environment for the learners, where they should use this chance as much as possible. However, some of the students find it difficult to speak in the target language for many reasons, ranging from interest to confidence, from age to knowledge. Other students, however, would like to express everything they think or feel by using the new language.

-While some students follow the lesson and are able to answer questions and do well in tests, others fall behind, don't seem to understand and do badly in tests.

- While some students pay attention and are cooperative, others 'misbehave' and seem disinterested.

- Teachers feel concerned that they are not challenging the high-achievers enough and at the same time are not giving enough help to those who are not doing as well.

- Teachers find it hard to 'pitch' their lessons at a level where all students can be engaged.

As a result, some students may take many turns, while others do not speak for the entire lesson. Teachers need to identify the problems of mixed ability classes and try to come out with the solutions of eliminating them. There are several strategies that a teacher can use to deal with the situation. This paper attempts to highlight the level of learning of English language, and the problems of teaching English at

polytechnic level in India and some suggestions also have been advocated in order to improve the overall English language learning and teaching situation in mixed ability classrooms. Every student has the right to be involved in the classroom activities irrespective of his or her personal capabilities. On the one hand, we don't have the right to neglect the pupils with little capabilities and, on the other hand, the lesson shouldn't be boring for the smart pupils. Realizing the importance of setting different demands for the pupils of mixed abilities, new three level standards for listening, speaking, reading and writing have been worked out in our country lately. Some strategies of work in classes of mixed abilities:

- The teacher should adapt some of the materials to make the language simple.
- Design own teaching materials. Use visual teaching materials to grab the students' attention and to motivate them to get interest in the subject.
- Vary the level of tasks to the slow learners. (eg) reduce the number of choices or should not give the more difficult choices in multiple level exercises.
- Form groups of weaker and stronger students separated from each other and give different tasks to these groups. (eg) Stronger and quicker students work with more complicated tasks, whereas the weaker students deal with a simpler task or work with the teacher as a group member.
- Try to know the learners, their language level and interests. Try to find every single student's strength by offering a variety of activities.
- Try to find the strengths and preferred learning style of everyone. Involve and encourage the shy learners. Extra work should be given of something that the students would enjoy doing on their favorite topic. They would be more enthusiastic to work on such projects.
- Help students, learn to respect diversity in terms of skills and abilities.

Apart from such practices, the following methods can also be adopted in the English language learning class.

-Self – respect: The attitude of a teacher who constantly corrects him may destroy the student’s self-esteem. A teacher is more effective when she or he is able to highlight the positive qualities of a student. It is important to point out the small success of the student, which may lead to big successes of tomorrow.

-Non – Correction Methods: In developing the skill of communication in English. If someone corrects a person as soon as he starts speaking, he will not be able to speak in front of other people for fear of making mistakes again. The best thing is to allow the person to speak at least the wrong English, so that he develops the habit of speaking the language.

- Word – Building : Every person who has to speak a language has three levels of word power built in gradually and steadily through experiencing the language. The first set of words is that which a person will be able to identify but may not know the correct meaning of, and hence hesitate to use while speaking or writing. These words are generally large in number. The second set of words is that which a person will be able to identify and understand the meaning of, but is unable to call to mind or use as the situation demands. The third set of words may be the half the number of second set. Care has to be taken to build up the word power of the student.

Experiential approaches to learning: Information, knowledge and wisdom reach us best through experience. Experiential learning is helpful in the case of linguistic skill development. When a person experience a language, it becomes easy for him to learn or speak it. When one considers teaching spoken English, one has to think of providing learning situations that will help the learner experience the language. The number of such opportunities to experience the language will decide the progress of learner’s skill in Speaking English.

Reading Comprehension : It is necessary to give an opportunity for each student to read loudly, so that it will be possible for the student to hear that words spoken by him. As the letters are identified and words recognized, student may continue to read but may not comprehend, so it is not essential that reading should

be practiced after testing whether a student can comprehend what he reads. And this will help the student to identify the answer easily for the leading questions.

Listening: These would include several types of conversations and speeches. The best available methods of recorded conversation can be provided. The conversations will be an imitation initially, but gradually, through repetitions, the student will outgrow the imitative method and attempt to speak by using his/her own words, structures and patterns.

Mind Skill Exercises : The connection between thought and expression is an important aspect that has to be considered whenever a student has to be helped in learning a language. Along with all such practices in the classrooms, the students should also be given exposure. There can be no learning without exposure. Group Discussions can be arranged. Texts should be read loudly by the students. The zeal for learning will help them in their own advancement. The problems of the learners and the teachers are inter-related. It is necessary to assure that the learner makes a tremendous contribution in the process. Some strategies of work in classes of mixed abilities:

The first strategy involves creating or providing different tasks for different levels. For example, the teacher can use a number of comprehension questions for a text. The teacher may have two sets of questions-A and B. Perhaps all students have to complete set A, the stronger ones also have to complete set B, or they even have an extra reading text. This obviously increases the amount of lesson preparation. For example, the teacher gives the students the text to read.

Financial Management

Henry Ford, a famous engineer and car producer, was grown up in a poor American farmer family with a very small budget. Eight children had to survive working hard in the farm. Being an intellectual, willing boy he coped with problems and took up producing cars: having produced the first automobile going by petrol Ford created a conveyer system of producing cars. Henry Ford

paid a great attention to financial management by improving his car industry. He spent his money on the productive, essential processes in car manufacturing. His famous motto “a car for everybody!” denied the idea that only the richest people could own cars! Ford made out a special technique to produce an automobile in a cheaper price by decreasing amount of money spent on it. As a result a proper financial management brought him and his company fame. Later Henry Ford had become one of the richest men in the world as well. After reading this text the stronger students have to do detailed dictionary work on the vocabulary of the text. With the stronger students spending 10 minutes working with dictionaries the teacher has time to monitor and help the weaker ones with the text. Then the teacher can go through the shared comprehension tasks for the class and perhaps the stronger students can make a presentation about the words they have researched. Now I want to speak about the extra work and homework. It is straightforward to give different students different homework. The teacher should give weaker students homework which really consolidates the class work and should give the stronger students work that will widen their knowledge. When teaching mixed ability classes the weaker students will be missing things during the lesson or failing to understand. And the teacher should use homework to address this. When nominating, the teacher should:

1. Ask the question before she gives the name of the student. In this case everyone has to listen;
2. Consider how easy it is for the student to answer. If a weak student will struggle, perhaps she should ask a stronger student. If a weak student should be capable, then she should ask them;
3. Avoid making students seem foolish, and yet also avoid patronizing them by only asking super simple questions;
4. Nominate with variety. The teacher should be careful to avoid nominating the same selection of students.

Conclusion. In a mixed level class the teacher can have different expectations of the language that the different students produce. Sometimes it can push the stronger students if the teacher corrects them heavily-although she should be sensitive about this.

Teachers mustn't neglect the pupils who are less capable than others. There are a great variety of classroom activities by means of which they can overcome the difficulty of mixed ability classes.

If we take into consideration the role of teacher and learner in acquiring the knowledge of a language, the problems can be solved effectively. Only then the students will realize the practical use of English language. English will be used by them as medium of expression. They will be able to use English as a language of communication. Fluency in the speech, proper knowledge of sentence structure, confidence of speaking in the public will make them able to keep their pace with the developing world. It will help in raising the standards of English as a language at the college level. Thus, the role of teacher at first is to identify and find out the effective strategies and to implement an active, interesting and interactive process of learning for the learners with different levels of ability. Teachers must have a healthy and congenial relationship with the students and it is always advisable to strike a balance between emotional and intellectual relationship with them. The teachers must teach, shape, motivate and recreate minds capable of facing challenges and to overcome the problems in the modern scenario.

REFERENCE

1. Якубов, Ф. У. (2014). Лингвистический принцип в теории перевода во взглядах немецких лингвистов. In *Актуальные вопросы современной науки* (pp. 237-241).
2. Yakubov, Fazliddin Utaganovich. "Improving communicative language skills through role playing activity." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 1006-1010.

3. Yakubov, F. U. (2022). Improving communicative language skills through role playing activity. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 1006-1010.
4. Qo'ychieva, Zuxra Isaqulovna. "Talabalarda liderlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning ayrim metodologik masalalari." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 908-913.
5. Qo'ychieva, Z. I. (2022). Talabalarda liderlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning ayrim metodologik masalalari. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 908-913.
6. Dusbayeva, Nazira Narimanovna. "Ingliz tilida mintaqaviy lugatlarni o'rganishning ahamiyati." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 706-709.
7. Dusbayeva, N. N. (2022). Ingliz tilida mintaqaviy lugatlarni o'rganishning ahamiyati. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 706-709.
8. Madiyeva, Gavhar Abdulazimovna. "Ta'limda yangi innovatsion modelni tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 777-780.
9. Madiyeva, G. A. (2022). Ta'limda yangi innovatsion modelni tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 777-780.
10. Mustafaqulova, Hulkar Ahmedovna. "Teaching culture in the ESL classroom." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 817-820.
11. Mustafaqulova, H. A. (2022). Teaching culture in the ESL classroom. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 817-820.
12. Хилолиддинова, Феруза Рашидовна. "Типы предложений и их классификация в английском языке." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 1413-1418.
13. Yakubov, Fazliddin. "THE LINGUISTIC PRINCIPLE IN THE THEORY OF TRANSLATION IN THE VIEWS OF GERMAN LINGUISTS." *InterConf* (2021).
14. Yakubov, F. (2021). THE LINGUISTIC PRINCIPLE IN THE THEORY OF TRANSLATION IN THE VIEWS OF GERMAN LINGUISTS. *InterConf*.
16. Boqiyeva, Rohila Bolabekovna. "Linguistic features of human internal concepts in English and Uzbek languages." *Science and Education* 3.2 (2022): 691-694.